

Role of Higher Education Commission in promotion of Education in Global Perspective: Analytical Study of Higher Education System of Pakistan

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Abstract

The burgeoning history of educational system of Pakistan echoes an ambivalent image of educational practices as well as vague policies at every stage. In 2002, university grants commission (UGC) got replaced with Higher education commission (HEC) and the focus of the government of Pakistan pivoted towards providing higher education. HEC came up with pragmatic and conclusive approach to eradicate education-related concerns. The prospective goal was the achievement of high-quality educational system to progress along the global educational framework. HEC, thus introduced variety of plans, programs, and projects in order to attain its goals. For example, designing of curriculum in accordance with the global perspective, admitting foreign academicians, underpinning, funding, and supporting arts, humanities, social sciences, IT, and their research domains, and domestic as well as foreign scholarship scheming are among the major roles contributed by HEC in promoting higher education in global perspective. Moreover, developmental schemes for highly-qualified and experienced faculty members, establishment of tenure track service (TTS) framework, commencement of learning innovation division are the progresses attained by HEC. Additionally, HEC has launched the courses highlighting the significance and execution of incorporation technology in Education. Also, HEC has established Quality assurance and quality enhancement cells in public and private educational sectors. The current study is thus focused upon exploring and highlighting the role of higher education commission in promoting higher education in Pakistan in the global perspective. Also, this paper delve into higher educational problems in Pakistan along with their viable way outs available in a revolutionary locale. As education is influential to the universally consolidative expansion and evolution of a state at every stage, therefore the scholars have queried and scrutinized the current educational framework whilst objectively monitoring, reviewing, as well as experiencing it. For this purpose, the current research is analytic, theoretical-cum-pragmatic, universally consolidative, and characteristically revolutionary.

Research Aims:

This examination has been planned to research and comprehend the various manners by which higher education changes were started, seen, conceptualized, executed, and qualified. The point of the examination is to discover the significant teamsters of the Higher education changes phenomenon that start and continue this cycle in the state and furthermore to uncover the significant changes presented in the earlier decade particularly in 2002, after the foundation of Higher Education Commission (HEC). This research study is designed with the aim to:

- Explore the Educational system of Higher Education Commission of Pakistan
- Analyzation of the current Educational System of Pakistan
- Explaining the Roles and responsibilities of Higher Education Commission of Pakistan in promoting education in global perspective
- Delve into the Challenges and constraints faced by the Pakistani educational institutions, faculty, and students
- Devise some solutions and future reforms for the educational challenges

Research Approach:

This research study concentrates on the descriptive review of educational framework of Higher Education Commission of Pakistan along with the investigative analysis of educational system of Pakistan. For this purpose, “overall assessment of the higher education sector” along with “Pakistan Higher Education Commission Vision 2025” has been utilized as the primary sources. Besides, various published journal articles as secondary sources are consulted for the literature regarding educational policies of HEC and educational frameworks of Pakistan. Based on the functions of HEC in educational structure, educational reforms brought about by HEC, analytical investigation of Pakistan educational framework, challenges faced by Pakistan’s education system, certain futuristic prospects are designed and discussed theoretically followed by the concluding remarks of the study. The study is designed in APA referencing style.

Introduction:

A consultative committee on the proposed vision of Higher Education Commission (HEC) was organized on 29 May, 2017. The report outlines the sector's desired objectives for the year 2017-2025. The aim was to develop a strategy for implementing the vision of HEC for 2025. This report contains a summary of the proposed policy and refers to new collaborative opportunities. The annex provides a comprehensive description of the strategy. In previous years, the educational system of Pakistan was extremely neglected and public investments were relatively scarce. The investment has improved since the foundation of HEC in 2002, with a new focus on the importance of educational institutions as promoters of socio-economic growth. In a 2002 executive order the functions, duties and practices of HEC are established. It has a wide range of capabilities and intends to:

- Establish strategies, basic principles and goals for the enhancement of socio-economic growth of universities;
- Recommend terms and conditions through which institutions can be established and governed, even those not within the government education system.
- Promote the progress, in a research-enhancing way, of interconnections between universities, industries and international and domestic associations.
- Evaluate the selection and distribution of degrees, certificates as well as diplomas issued by national and international institutions.
- Promote accessibility for faculties through national and foreign interactions, develop initiatives including the distribution of funding to create scholarships, financial aid as well as visiting professorship programs or other similar programs.
- Support systematic affiliations between public institutions to use expertise and advanced facilities most effectively, and to foster regional and international relations in the areas of information sharing, strategic analysis, resource exchange as well as cost-sharing.

The Vision 2025 of HEC represents this scope and places HEC at the center of a huge scale systematic strategy to the growth of education system in Pakistan for the next 8 years. Higher education funding is also inadequate according to international expectations in Pakistan. Grant for higher education has increased from 0.09 percent in 2001-2002 to 0.3 percent in 2015-2016 of the total GDP. It is a rise from PKR 3.9 billion to PKR 87.9 billion of the overall grants. There are some references for comparison with World Bank results. The worldwide average is 1.02% of GDP, however for Pakistan, it is 0.8%. To be clear, the 2012-2013 HEC funding is set at 0.2% of GDP and cannot thus be used as a subsidiary for public spending on tertiary learning by the World Bank for years in which the information is not available. HEC's website identifies 183 universities in Pakistan, including 108 public institutions and 75 private institutions. There is a wide difference in all areas of the industry and the whole sector. Nevertheless, public higher education institutes typically provide a broad variety of programs and courses, while private higher education institutes provide a limited selection of programs and courses that have a technical focus such as IT or business. This variation in scope may be evident in Pakistan's success in international ranks. There is low performance of the entire national system, however the ranked institutes are publicly financed. Data from a number of sources on enrolments indicate that the percentage of enrolled students has increased considerably:

- The UNESCO Statistics Institute recorded a net enrollment rise from 2.7% in 2003 to 9.9% in 2015.
- HEC records a 47% increase in the overall number of students enrolled in universities either on campus or by distance learning programs from 2001-2002 to 2014-2015.

Probably, much of the development in the span of 2001-2002 to 2014-2015 has been produced by government and private students on campus. The highest rise in students enrolled in distance-learning programs was, however, seen, but this figure decreased during 2013-2015. The shortage of trained higher education teaching personnel raises obstacles to continuing enrollment growth and maintaining the overall efficiency of higher education system. According to HEC, 26.9% of full-time staff had a doctorate in 2012-2013, although the distribution varies by area and mode of delivery.

Literature review:

Higher Education Commission (HEC) of Pakistan

Higher education is a vital guiding factor imagined making the idea of an information-based economy a fact, and this also leads to the achievement of society's common objectives, promoting unity, and developing good citizens. Furthermore, it has played a tremendous part in the growth of states as a common benefit, empowering people with cultural norms, traditions, and public values, and encouraging them to benefit mankind. Generally, it has been regarded as a general welfare, serving not just the people who received education, but the entire population in terms of the enormous contributions to society. This viewpoint on higher education has become a prevalent opinion on the roles and importance of higher education as a common benefit, it was also recognised as a fundamental civil right in the United Nations' Universal Declaration on Human Rights (1948). Ever since 1950s, higher education has been seen as a profitable economic asset rather than a socially beneficial knowledge or a fundamental human right throughout several regions of the world. It's worth is measured in respect of economic benefits to the founders of private higher education institutes. Private higher education institutes tacit goals are to achieve full market share to manage financial activities by offering degrees at different rates, at the expense of efficiency. Private higher education institutes in Pakistan have grown at an unprecedented rate, especially since the foundation of the Higher Education Commission (HEC). The main task of the Higher Education Commission was to serve for the assessment, enhancement, and advancement of higher education by illustrating a system of research & innovation within higher education institutes. Furthermore, the HEC develops laws, strategies, values, and goals for higher education institutes in Pakistan in order to promote socio-economic growth. Furthermore, amid HEC administrative laws and regulations, private higher education institutes in Pakistan market higher education just as commercial product at a number of price ranges, with little regard for customer satisfaction. As a result, in recent years, the privatisation of higher educational system in Pakistan has sparked controversy. In terms of declining higher educational system as a public benefit, commercialization of the higher educational system has become a personal asset whose worth is measured by financial rewards. In recent times, because of this selfish approach, the efficiency is sacrificed for the sake of financial benefit. Furthermore, privatization of the higher educational institutes has resulted in profit-seeking corporations that sacrifice morals and values for short-term monetary advantages, instilling in community a sense of materialism manipulative reasoning, greed, envy, and dominance. Education has indeed been turned into a product, along with many other essentials of existence, to be purchased and sold solely for benefit, and it has also resulted in dramatic shifts in how culture defines the impact of knowledge on humanity and how it has been passed on and developed."

Evaluation of the Educational Structure in Pakistan

Pakistan had just one university when it was established in 1947: the University of Punjab that was established in the city of Lahore. However, there are now almost 50 governmental and non - governmental universities, as well as 18 other degree-granting institutes. Degree programs in science and technology, engineering, medical, pharmacy, law as well as business administration are available at the majority of private universities and schools. In 2005, less than 4.6% of students between the ages of 17 to 23 years were enrolled in higher educational programs. Public colleges, which are owned and sponsored by the government, however comprised of 85% of all students enrolled in higher educational programs. Colleges, among which 88% are paid by the government, comprise about 71% of all students who are enrolled in higher level courses. Higher education institutions are associated with colleges. All the college students are now also enrolled in the associated institutions. Thus, the university's net attendance includes attendance of students in the associated colleges as well as attendance in the university programs. This demonstrates that private higher educational institutes as well as the affiliated schools and colleges account for 15% of overall admissions, while non-government institutions including university departments account for 29%. Given the current trend of population expansion, Pakistan will have about 25 million students between the age of 17 and 23, necessitating the establishment of a number of institutes and programs. Strategies have been proposed to increase exposure to higher educational system to at least 10% for this age group in order to improve the nation's human capital. Since the government cannot offer adequate financing, major expansion and diversified courses are deemed necessary, as well as an increase in the involvement of the private sector can also help increase the availability of quality education to all students. Identifying this, the state reversed its 1970 policy to nationalize educational schools, allowing private institutes to execute, in 1980. The state mostly funds general education programs which are largely offered by state universities. Around 75% of the overall resources available was used to pay the staff and other workers' wages (Government of Pakistan 2002). The majority of public higher educational funding comes from government funding administered by the University Grants Commission (UGC), which was established in the early 1950s to finance higher educational institutes. The majority of developmental funds are invested on universities, among which only about 700 undergraduate institutions receiving any assistance. Despite this, the government has been reluctant to adequately finance higher educational institutes, and institutions increased their self-generated revenues to 49% of overall spending in 2000–2001. Since the previous two decades, state funding on education has hovered about 2% of GNP, well below the 4% of GNP suggested by UNESCO (Government of Pakistan (2001) as well as the 3.4% of GNP

recorded by the South Asia in 1995 (World Bank–UNESCO, 2000). Higher educational institutes accounts for just about 0.4% of GNP. It comes as no surprise that students of state funded universities receive an inferior education which does not allow them to engage adequately in the states economic, financial, and social activities or to meet the demands of a dynamic world economy. In regard to the growing demand for new and realistic education in business and marketing, private institutions typically pay huge wages to employees and have high-quality libraries and laboratory services in 1983, Agha Khan University was founded as Pakistan's only private-sector university which was later followed by Lahore University of Management Sciences. The governments education reforms (2001–2004) projected an increase in relative enrollment in the private-sector institutions from 15% to 40% at the end of 2004 by promoting the introduction of new higher educational institutes in private sector. As a result, the privatization process accelerated, and at the end of 2004, 53 degree-granting universities in Pakistan had enrolled approximately 4.6% of the students between ages of 17 to 23. The National Education Policy(1998–2010) raised public support from 2.2% to 4% of GNP, extended services to accommodate at least 5% of the specific age group, and established a three-year master (honors) degree, with honors students given priority in enrollment and state hiring. Higher education institutions were requested to raise their own money, and limitations were to be eliminated. The Higher Education Commission (HEC) was founded to help institutions grow into world-class centers of science and technology. The HEC's mandate includes all degree-granting colleges and universities, both public and private, as well as degree-granting schools. It helps these institutes achieve academic excellence by encouraging and arranging self-assessment of degree programs with an independent evaluation by national and foreign specialists. The HEC also oversees the strategy, growth, and certification of undergraduate and post - graduate institutions, whether government or non- government.

Current roles and responsibilities of HEC in the promotion of Higher Education in Pakistan

Higher education in our system is way of provision of motivational vision that has potential to turn dreams into reality in content of knowledge-based reality and contribution in accomplishment of collective goals of mankind, creating union and establishing better human being. The major function of higher education is provision of trained labor force, implementation of modern ways to impart new knowledge and exceptional societal services for development of economy. Education plays fundamental role in setting moral and economic framework of any group of people. Essential and critical goal of advanced education is to assemble the building of the country, by giving mindfulness, giving contemporary scholarly idea, and fill in as research organizations to public and private area. Most significant capacity of advanced education is to make, and disperse new information through quality exploration, as advanced education establishments are viewed as logical, and social labs of information creation. From economy viewpoint, advanced education should satisfy the needs of industry by giving better quality HR having proficient and specialized abilities. By and huge, advanced education foundations should construct moral character, by instilling moral and virtues, attitudinal qualities for socializations of people for the assurance and improvement of cultural qualities. Another significant capacity of advanced education is to adapt to worldwide, by demonstrating feasible and even minded answers for public and global issues and issues. In nutshell, advanced education should serve the public interest from all points of view socially, financially, socially, and strategically. Subsequently it is viewed as a respectable public assistance, and advanced education establishments are reference point places of learning and it very well may be presumed that the essential target of advanced education foundation is to make a general public where the majority of the understudies are gifted, and advanced education organizations are able to produce new information.

Challenges and Suggested reforms in future educational milieu

Less qualified teachers and lack of professional training

The teacher being a good example and a wellspring of motivation, must be an appropriately qualified, knowledgeable coach in the picking up educating measure. Shockingly, in Pakistan, at all essential three levels, this fundamental profession is embraced by individuals who do not fit well for some other occupation. That is the reason the burdensome duty is not really carried capability by them. Subsequently, their educating, preparing, and sustaining great Pakistanis, practically gets troublesome. To improve the norm of Pakistani instruction, free and reasonable, critical, and merit-based straightforward rules must be advanced, with the goal that lone expertly capable alumni can join the good forum. Furthermore, qualified educators ought to be given serious pay rates and motivations based on their exhibition and results. Thirdly, in-administration preparing, supplemental classes and polished methodology should likewise get basic to the instructing and examination vocation. Instructors' preparation is vital for teachers, yet additionally for school and college educators. These fundamental strides for arrangement, enlistment and preparing, can assist with expanding the nature of instructors and their skill at various levels in the Pakistani arrangement of schooling. Most importantly, an Education Service is fundamental at the common and government levels, at part with partner Civil Services.

Insufficient funds and misuse of budgetary allocation

UNESCO, a prominent body suggest a set proportion for schooling and proficiency but unfortunately The Government of Pakistan has been assigning under 04% of the Gross Domestic Product to training, which is even beneath the suggestive proportion. Indeed, even the said low budgetary allotment is not delivered to and spent on teaching, appropriately. Accordingly, the essential points for development of good platform lacked in many ways for instance the goals of the enlistment of qualified instructors, foundation of new instructive establishments, giving them the fundamental framework, educators preparing and delivering quality alumni, are badly crushed In Pakistan, social area advancement in schooling, wellbeing and fundamental necessities has been disregarded in the yearly monetary spending plan, on account of which it could not advance throughout the long term. Conversely, the spot of the state arrangement of instruction has been taken by private instructive establishments, which are business deeply. Many are packed, notwithstanding charging substantial expenses. Quality is undermined over amount, prompting the mushrooming of instructive establishments and institutions. An administrative authority involving specialists from the foundation, money, law, and training should screen the financial plan apportioned for schooling, and its straightforward use. The private arrangement of instruction at all levels, essential, optional, and tertiary, should be observed and managed, for indigenization and Pakistanisation

Curriculum designing

Curriculum planning is a most significant errand in instructive arranging, strategy, and practice. Educational programs shift for various surges of training in Pakistan. The conventional standard is primarily founded on repetition learning and packing. Understudies with an industrious memory can undoubtedly clear the assessments, yet those with an intelligent learning limit and inventive ability can discover the circumstance troublesome. Educational programs are a different and disruptive blend and seldom take into account the public instructive and monetary necessities. They just serve the few incendiary streams and frameworks previously talked about, basically elitist, and "awami" or for the destitute individuals. On occasion, the courses are acquired and imported, and are not contextualized in the Pakistani climate. Neither do they center the Eastern Values System nor Islam as a religion of humankind and human instinct. The first class are socio-socially, broadly, and strictly distanced and commonly, materialistically estranging, being Western and Westernizing. Instructive establishments do not offer all-encompassing integrative training: scholarly, mainstream, profound, physical, enthusiastic and moral-material. An understudy's perception is not inspected critically, artificially, and scientifically. Or maybe, it is assessed based on memory. Additionally, the educational plans continue evolving arbitrarily quickly, as new ones are out of nowhere presented all of a sudden, while understudies are just part of the way through the current courses. The upsides and downsides of such changes and corrections are not surveyed subjectively by a board of specialists in the applicable field. This causes challenges for both the instructors, and the guardians of understudies, who cannot stand to purchase new books with offbeat changes in the educational plans. This is more regrettable from the perspective of assessments..

System of examination as well as evaluation

Examination system in any education is the outcome of scholastic studying as well as teaching. In Pakistan, the system of examination is in subjective format as well as/or objective format, also, can be the combination of these two formats, encompassing a main section of the syllabi being taught. Students with good cramming ability get good grades. However, the others lag behind, despite of their excellent other class activities and learning periods. In the examination system, summative analysis is emphasized the most, rather than the formative analysis. Embezzlement or duplicating is just another downfall of exam system, that hinders the talent from growing. The staff supervising or invigilating the exams is either corrupted, tortured, or contacted by the corrupters for the disloyal benefits. Therefore, security must be given to the staff for transparent conductance of exams. Hardworking understudies are demoralized and dissuaded because of such circumstances. A specific open book exam scheme, where appropriate, should be deemed. Similarly, papers system must investigate and analyze the creativity, comprehension, understanding, and originality of the subject as well as fundamental skills related to language together with the creative imagining.

Standard of educational training

The matter of standard of educational training in schools, colleges, and universities has persisted to be the controversial issue since the Pakistan independence in 1947. The advocates of English and Urdu have been opposing one another. For the rationalization of the state of affairs, the planners of educational system should take both advocacies into consideration, while formulating the policy at every level of education. Urdu is the national language of Pakistan, while English is the official language for the domains of education, formulation of policies, technology, commerce, diplomacy, economics, science, trade, and media. These languages should made to contribute accordingly to the educational domain of Pakistan. The codes of language, conduct, and behavior are the pivotal commodities of national identification. Therefore, including both languages in national curricula is highly advisable from primary up to higher educational standards along with the other regional

dialects of Pakistan at every grade for better outcomes at local and national levels. Skilled English and Urdu languages faculty must be employed for this aim. Additional classes for the training of different languages are recommended that should focus upon basic skill sets of language. Computer Assisted Language Learning i.e., CALL might be taken into consideration as well. The implementation of this technique would be contributing in the integration of the training standards as well in the educational sectors of Pakistan with the purpose of promoting national unification as well as social cohesion. Relevant to the psychology of education, basic and primary education is very progressive in mother-father dialect

Global perspective of Educational Reformatations:

The era of nineteenth century can be designated as the era of globalization, commercialization, and competition. These parameters have laid an influence upon the functional frameworks of numerous states in the perspective of economic, cultural, and political contexts. The globalization phenomenon has brought about enhancement of educational systems and granted importance to knowledge as well as information, the fundamental financial entities for advancements and development of any state around the globe. The educational field possess pivotal rank in the educational economy because for progressing in this innovative economic restructuring man's finances are important. The worldwide nations considers the matter of education as of fundamental significance due to its pivotal and important rank of education in development of the nations. The OECD, World Bank, United nations, and UNESCO being the super state agencies have been continuously engaged in underpinning the significance of education for the worldwide states. UNESCO together with the World bank arranged a collaborative conference in 2000. In this conference the governments of all the participating states settled upon guaranteeing education to every citizen by the launch and summit of collaborative responsibilities

Conclusion

Education is the safe base for a country's financial turn of events and quiet advancement. It is all around viewed as a significant device of groundbreaking change which has a solid connection with the general social and monetary advancement of a nation. It can assist with improving the scholastic quality and exploration work of understudies, researchers and scientists. The Pakistan government started different sound and reasonable education arrangements since 1947, putting assets in them. But since the absence of legitimate execution and financing activity, no productive outcomes have been accomplished. Little consideration has been paid to the educators' capability and preparing, actual framework of educational establishments, and appropriate grounds culture, managerial administration, disciplinary implicit rules, keeping up legitimacy and restricting political exercises and impacts. All the educational policies, programs, and reformatations introduced and practiced by Higher Education Commission (HEC) of Pakistan indicates that still there needs some improvements and certain reformatations has to be made to copwith the contemporary globalized world. Additionally, the finances available to run education at higher level are insufficient and hence a basic hinderance in tackling the issued related to the education at higher level. In light of the current flawed education strategy in real life, the imaginative ability of Pakistani understudies and researchers is squandered woefully. Subsequently, cerebrum channel for better freedoms and greener fields abroad, gets enticing. Education strategy must be focused on by the public approach, arranging and work on, keeping in consideration the National Ideology and Interest. Basically, educational difficulties are colossal in Pakistan. The arrangement producers and influencers are required to give realistic answers for improving the nature of education, at standard with territorial and global norms.

Recommendations

The educational prospective can be predictable and anticipated as indicated by the over a significant time span proceeding with patterns and certain processes, and new emanant or broken ones, to a reasonable logical degree. Insightful devices dependent on measurements and coherent techniques have been concocted to anticipate and project what is to come. In getting ready for the future, organizers set destinations and decide the level to which they are achievable, as indicated by the public asset limit and human ability. In arranging and filtering the alluring outcomes, organizers receive one of the option best prospects as an objective to accomplish. In the event that Pakistan is to endure economically as a sovereign state-social framework, in the 21st century and further, in the third thousand years, at that point opportune public arrangement and arranging is required. This is very conceivable in a truly just country which is completely useful, broadly, and devotedly, just as modernly. Normal, experienced, broadly philosophical, and astute contributions from the intellectuals and specialists is fundamental, to control the aggregate political authority, since the entirety of the skill and specialization that strategy detailing, arranging and practice involve. Every one of the partners must be accepted for getting, guaranteeing, and settling Pakistan's sovereign, key, independent future. Several recommendations are proposed for numerous domains including planning, administration, allocation of funds, faculty improvement, quality of educational sectors, and partnership of public and private institutions.

- For the improvement of education at higher level globally, faculty of colleges as well as universities must devise a strategy subject at delineating fair as well as equitable methods and unbiased techniques of culpability.
- The Higher Education Commission must possess an external advisory committee for the guidelines of procedures of decision-making and to ensure the transparency of such decisions.
- The external committee of HEC must find out the suitable methods and programs to be implemented for guaranteeing success.
- The bodies of national accreditation should seek to investigate the educational sectors in accordance with the international criteria, also to endorse the educational sectors more meticulously.
- Research must be planned for the whole state.
- Educational costs for every understudy must be computed prudently so that the students can manage the funds in accordance with them.
- The funds of Higher Education Commission for the educational institutions must be established in relevance to the degree programs as well the ranks of faculty.
- The students of private sector institutions must be eligible for the proposed scholarships as well as stipends.
- The corporate divisions must be urged to provide funds for the educational purposes.
- Remuneration for the faculty must be made better.
- More and more development as well as training programs must be organized.
- Teaching Personnel ought to be urged to redesign training approach and educational programs utilizing basic reasoning and issue-based learning patterns.
- For improving the quality of institutions state-of-the-art resources must be provided to them.
- Furthermore, physical framework of the educational institutions ought to be technically adequate.
- Private educational institutions must share the expertise of their teaching personnel with that of the public educational institutions.
- Private educational institutions must give education to the understudies from under-privileged divisions with the help of need-based grants.
- Institutions getting funds from HEC should utilize those funds after getting the approval from the Governors' board and present a report to education commission related to their management.

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